

Gameflow

- **1 INDIVIDUAL DECISIONS ON PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION**
- **2 IS THERE AN EVENT?**
Checking the cards in the yellow or red stack
- **3 RESULTS: POINTS AND STATE OF BIODIVERSITY**
Calculating the results based on players' decisions
- **4 COMMUNITY COUNCIL FOR DISCUSSION**
Time for discussing anything important and not important
- **5 REFERENDUM**
Deciding on keeping or removing Governor from office
- **6 IF REFERENDUM REQUIRED OR IF TERM EXPIRED: ELECTION**
Who would like to run for Governor's office? Let's vote
- **7 GOVERNOR'S DECISION: CHANGING OR KEEPING POLICIES**
Governor in office decides on Policies for the next round

Policy

Land Policy	
High land availability	Low land availability

Tax Policy	
Low taxes	High taxes

Governance

Current Governor			
Producer 1	Producer 2	Producer 3	
Consumer 1	Consumer 2	Consumer 3	Consumer 4

Current Governor Term		
Term 1	Term 2	Term 3

State of Biodiversity

- Production is more than 120
- - → Production is 120 points or less

High Biodiversity

Event likelihood: 0%

Reduced Biodiversity

Event likelihood: 30%

Low Biodiversity

Event likelihood: 80%

Cut out the tokens below. Alternatively, you can use small round objects such as whiteboard magnets or coins, which may make the game easier to play. You will need 4 tokens for the Governance Board and 1 token for the State of Biodiversity Board.

Tokens for the Governance board

Token for the State of Biodiversity board

**High
Consumption**

**75
Base Points**

**Low
Consumption**

60
Base Points

**High
Consumption**

45
Base Points

**Low
Consumption**

30
Base Points

Natural Area

Farm 1

Farm 2

Farm 3

Low land availability

High land availability

**High Intensity
Agriculture**

100
Base Points

**High Intensity
Agriculture**

100
Base Points

**High Intensity
Agriculture**

100
Base Points

**Low Intensity
Agriculture**

80
Base Points

**Low Intensity
Agriculture**

80
Base Points

**Low Intensity
Agriculture**

80
Base Points

**High Intensity
Agriculture**

60
Base Points

**High Intensity
Agriculture**

60
Base Points

**High Intensity
Agriculture**

60
Base Points

**Low Intensity
Agriculture**

40
Base Points

**Low Intensity
Agriculture**

40
Base Points

**Low Intensity
Agriculture**

40
Base Points

**Tax &
Investments**

**Tax &
Investments**

**Tax &
Investments**

**Tax &
Investments**

Rewilding Area
Diverse Trees, Bushes and Flowers

Rewilding Area
Diverse Trees, Bushes and Flowers

Rewilding Area
Diverse Trees, Bushes and Flowers

Low Biodiversity

Note: Place the next 10 ten cards (8 event cards and 2 non-event cards) under this cover card.

Epidemic

More contact with the wild animals that lost their habitats triggered a new epidemic.

Drought

Increasingly poor soil that could not hold moisture together with warmer climate caused severe droughts.

Hurricane

Fewer natural buffers in the form of diverse plants could not protect well against a hurricane.

Wildfire

Monoculture crops and trees accelerated the spread of wildfires and their spill into residential areas.

Blizzard

Snow blankets, freezing temperatures and strong winds damaged the key crops.

Landslide

Almost no trees on the hills led to soil erosion. Masses of rock and mud buried much of the town.

Sinkhole

A large area of ground suddenly collapsed, swallowing buildings, roads, and anything in its vicinity.

Heatwave

Extreme temperatures, energy crises and few trees in town led to dehydration, heat strokes and fatalities.

No Event

A landslide hit the neighbouring village but luckily your community is not affected.

No Event

There has been a severe hurricane across the region but luckily your community is not affected.

Reduced Biodiversity

Note: Place the next 10 ten cards (3 event cards and 7 non-event cards) under this cover card.

Pest Infestation

This year there has been not enough birds and the pest attack destroyed many crops.

No Event

Very worrying forecasts about wildfires in the forests surrounding your community luckily did not come true.

No Event

This year saw your region hit by a very strong heatwave but the microclimate in your community remained unaffected.

No Event

A massive flood devastated many parts of your region but with some luck your community is not affected.

No Event

An epidemic is spreading in the south of the country but your community seem to be safe so far.

Food Shortage

With almost no bees in town there was a very low agricultural yield this year leading to hunger and panic.

Flood

Reduced areas of wetlands meant that during high-water season, the town flooded.

No Event

This year there have been more sudden sinkholes in your region. Luckily your community has not yet experienced such a disaster.

No Event

Worsening soil quality is reinforcing severe droughts in your neighbouring communities, but you seem to be safe so far.

No Event

A massive blizzard paralyses the region harming much of agriculture. Yet you seem to have weathered the storm.

Consumer 1

You are a working parent of two and you juggle your job and family responsibilities. You try to make eco-conscious choices when possible, but convenience often takes precedence in your busy life.

Consumer 2

You are a retiree, divorced with three grown children. You have worked very hard to establish your own business for several decades. You prioritise supporting regional farmers' markets and are concerned about changes in the country. You expect the government to be active to protect local interests.

Consumer 3

You are single; you are passionate about sustainable living and an advocate for social justice, especially on topics related to migration and relations between Global North and Global South. You are conscious of your carbon footprint and try to make decisions that are ethically right and environmentally sustainable.

Consumer 4

You came for studies from abroad about 10 years ago and stayed here with many different jobs afterwards. You are married but your family has not yet migrated with you. You are open to embrace innovation and you value personal freedom.

Farmer 1

You are a seasoned farmer who has adapted to changing agricultural trends over the years. You prioritise efficiency and productivity on your farm while also incorporating some pro-environmental practices especially when this does not mean losing profit. You value balance and pragmatism in your approach to farming.

Farmer 2

You are a first-generation farmer who took over a larger farm and are passionate about organic farming. You value being outdoors, spending time with farm animals, planting diverse trees, and other nature-related activities. You are actively involved in community outreach and education programmes promoting sustainable farming practices.

Farmer 3

You come from a long line of farmers and are deeply rooted in traditional agricultural practices. You value hard work, self-sufficiency, and continuing your family's legacy. You are cautious about embracing new technologies and prefer to stick to tried-and-true farming methods. You value nuanced expertise that comes with generations of experience.

Extreme Poverty	Poverty	Stability	Relative Wealth	Wealth	Significant Wealth
You cannot cover your basic needs. You are starving.	You cover your basic needs. You are vulnerable to unexpected situations.	Your basic needs are covered. You are also able to save a little for emergencies.	You can afford occasional luxuries. You can save for emergencies.	You often enjoy luxuries. You can handle most emergencies and have resources to invest.	Luxury is routine. You have hardly any worries about emergencies. Maintaining wealth is your focus.
Consumers	0	25	35	45	65
Producers	0	30	40	60	85

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7
Farmer 1							
Farmer 2							
Farmer 3							
Consumer 1							
Consumer 2							
Consumer 3							
Consumer 4							

Wealth

